

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: in this article, the problems of reforming education at the level of modern demand, raising its quality to the level of high demand are thoroughly considered, and national and foreign experience in the training of highly qualified personnel is widely covered. The article also shows the main features that determine the quality of the educational process in the training of highly qualified personnel.

Keywords: innovation technology, emergency, natural disaster, accident, fire, earthquake.

Introduction: One of the priorities of the national state policy of our country is to protect the population and territories from natural and man-made emergencies, ensure security, achieve sustainable economic development. This entails the preliminary identification of emergency situations and the conduct of effective measures to warn the population of this danger, quick action in the event of an emergency, the Prevention of human sacrifice, low economic damage, timely security. In this regard, a number of good deeds are being carried out by our government under the leadership of our President. In particular, on August 20, 2020, by the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 515 "on the further improvement of the state system for the Prevention of emergency situations and action in such situations", the FVDT Charter was approved.

Relevance of the topic: In order to further improve the preschool education system, strengthen the material and technical base, expand the network of preschool educational institutions, provide qualified pedagogical personnel, radically improve the level of training of children for school education, apply modern educational programs and technologies to the educational process, create conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children. Protection of the life and health of preschool children raising them as a mature and competent person is a modern requirement.

The formation of foundations for the safety and life of children in a preschool educational organization is an urgent and important problem. It is important not only to protect the child from danger, but also to prepare him to face possible difficulties, to form an idea of the most dangerous situations, the need to take precautions, to instill in him the skills of safe behavior. In the preschool organization, the concept of security previously included only protection of the life and health of children. But the modern world has changed the approach to the problem of security, it has included such concepts as environmental disasters and terrorism.

As of 1 January 2023, the total number of children aged 0-14 in Uzbekistan is 10,178,910. Boys – 5,273,520, girls-4,905,398. The sad situation is that in January-April of

this year, the number of road accidents involving children in Uzbekistan is increasing by 25.3 percent, and the number of children killed in them is increasing by 64.5 percent. As of 2022, 175 dive-related accidents have been recorded, of which (34%) are minors.

7.2% of accidents caused by fires are caused by child abuse. As a result of unattended, neglect of children, disasters such as Burns, swallowing, related accidents (drugs, buttons, small toys, detergents), falling off the balcony, pinching fingers, toe clenches, and vas hu occur.

More than a million people, children are dying as a result of earthquakes taking place around the world.

In conclusion from the above, it is an urgent matter for children to seriously pay attention to the issues of desecration, measures to protect them from situations, everyday urges, to prevent them.

Main part: As an object of research, I received Dmtt 332, which is located in the Mirzo Ulugbek district. A total of 420 children from 3 to 6 to 7 were raised in the institution and 48 workers were employed.

There are cozy and beautiful rooms for children when I look at the object, and there are evacuation exits and a playground, while inside the building there are evacuation plans, fire safety corners. Children's lecture rooms have safe corners, bouquets of all kinds of dangers, visual weapons of Traffic Safety. The institution has every opportunity for children to be educated but not enough emergency training materials, toys and visual aids. Innovative methods are not used in lesson processes. When I received a survey from educators, I expressed the opinion that there were only pictures to undergo training, that there were not enough training materials, and that emergency classroom training should be included in the curriculum.

Analysis and results. A number of classes were held on the practical application of the content and essence of the modern organization of the preschool educational organization. a lesson on the topic "Emergency Situations" was conducted for children on the basis of the following tasks.

- 1. Assignment:** "tell me what professions are these?". Through the assignment, children find and remember the owners of professions related to the topic.
- 2. Assignment:** "evaluate and analyze the problem situation." Through these pictures, children learn, describe and assess the problem situation to the surface and why it happened.
- 3. Assignment:** the method of using Multimedia tools makes it possible to further herniate the perception of danger in children and create a primary skill in them about protection in the event of emergencies of different shades.

In the preparatory group of the preschool organization there were 32 educators, in the next group there were 35 educators, and in the last preparatory group there were 35 educators, and I chose one of the groups for the test. At the beginning of our experiments, we determined the following view of the level of assimilation of those brought up in preparatory groups. The first table shows the results of question answers from children.

The indicators obtained at the end of the experiment showed that the modern organization of preschool educational activities not only serves to increase their level of knowledge, but also positively affects the formation and development of game activity, psychophysiological features, including thinking, memory. We can see this based on the following table:

Table 1. The result of questions and answers from children

Selections	Caregivers number	Satisfactory	Good	excellent
Preparatory group	32	21	9	2

Table 2. In the second table, following didactic and explanatory rates results

Selections	Caregivers number	Satisfactory	Good	excellent
Preparatory group	32	7	19	6

Table 3. The third table lists the result obtained through multimedia

Selections	Caregivers number	Satisfactory	Good	excellent
Preparatory group	32	2	8	22

Drawing conclusions from the above, we focused our experimental work on the following.

1. Our observations show that assignments on the above topics were conducted on the basis of oral tests and didactic assignments.
2. At the beginning of the experiment, 5.97 percent achieved mastering, and at the end of the experiment, 80.59 percent achieved mastering.

1 Picture. Pre-and post-experimental results diagram.

Conclusions and recommendations: “methods of innovative education” refers to interactive methods that serve to independently solve the pedagogical problem posed to those who are trained in the study of preschool educational activities.

1. The most optimal way to achieve the effectiveness of literary education is the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching science classes in preschool educational organizations.

2. With the modern organization of activities of the preschool educational organization, educators develop effective communication and correct, fluent, expressive statement of their opinion, as well as basic defense skills.

3. The effectiveness of education depends on the thorough assimilation by educators of theoretical and practical knowledge on the foundations of the theory of modern pedagogical technology.

4. Modern methods activate the tarbilanists, who become more aware of the essence of small stories in the midst of a mutual controversy.

6. The need and skills of children to work together arise when activities are organized in cooperation with educators, small groups are organized, assignments are given not to a separate educator, but to small groups.

1. It is necessary to pay attention to the methodology of modern organization of preschool educational activities in a practical-methodological way and to expand the scope of the possibilities of conducting activities on the basis of a competency approach of educators.

2. Before organizing the training of preschool educational organization in interactive ways, special training seminars should be held on the premises, which are intended to purposefully and effectively organize the innovative activities of educators.

3. To create a methodological guide entitled “technologies for the modern organization of activities of the preschool educational organization” in order to arm educators with modern technologies of preschool children.

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